

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025
oktyabr

TOSHKENT SHAHRIDAGI TURIN
POLITEXNIKA UNIVERSITETI

*Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy onlayn konferensiya
materiallari to'plami*

“GLOBAL RAQAMLI INTEGRATSIYALASHUV:
2030-YILGACHA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA
TEXNOLOGIK VA INDUSTRIAL SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH
ORQALI MIKRO VA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQAROR
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH DOLZARBLIGI”

“GLOBAL DIGITAL INTEGRATION: THE RELEVANCE OF
ENSURING MICRO AND MACROECONOMIC SUSTAINABLE
GROWTH THROUGH TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL
DEVELOPMENT IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN
ECONOMY BY 2030”

«ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ ЦИФРОВАЯ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ:
АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО
МИКРО- И МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА ЧЕРЕЗ
РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ИНДУСТРИАЛЬНОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ
ЭКОНОМИКЕ К 2030 ГОДУ»

7-MAXSUS SON

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr.
2025-yil, oktyabr.

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afforovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
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- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

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REGULATORY AND LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich

Independent Researcher at Bukhara State Technical University
and Director of the 2nd Technical College of Bukhara City, Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0009-0008-1008-1226

E-mail: asqad.ataqulov@gmail.com

Abstract. This thesis examines the regulatory and legal foundations of product quality management in Uzbekistan. It analyzes the role of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law “On Consumer Rights Protection,” and special legislation on metrology, standardization, and technical regulation in ensuring access to safe and high-quality products. The study highlights the importance of improving legal mechanisms, strengthening institutional coordination, developing regional quality control laboratories, training qualified specialists, and promoting a quality culture among consumers and producers.

Keywords: product quality, quality management, consumer protection, metrology, standardization, technical regulation, legal framework, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisda O‘zbekistonda mahsulot sifatini boshqarishning normativ-huquqiy asoslari tahlil qilingan. Unda O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi, “Iste’molchilarning huquqlarini himoya qilish to‘g‘risida”gi Qonun hamda metrologiya, standartlashtirish va texnik jihatdan tartibga solish sohasidagi maxsus qonunlarning xavfsiz va sifatli mahsulotlar ta’minotidagi o‘rni yoritilgan. Tadqiqotda huquqiy mexanizmlarni takomillashtirish, institutsional hamkorlikni kuchaytirish, hududiy sifat nazorati laboratoriyalarini rivojlantirish, malakali mutaxassislar tayyorlash va sifat madaniyatini shakllantirish muhimligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: mahsulot sifati, sifatni boshqarish, iste’molchilar huquqlarini himoya qilish, metrologiya, standartlashtirish, texnik tartibga solish, huquqiy asoslar, O‘zbekiston.

Аннотация. В данном тезисе рассмотрены нормативно-правовые основы управления качеством продукции в Узбекистане. Проанализирована роль Конституции Республики Узбекистан, Закона «О защите прав потребителей», а также специальных законов в области метрологии, стандартизации и технического регулирования в обеспечении населения безопасной и качественной продукцией. В работе обоснована важность совершенствования правовых механизмов, укрепления институционального взаимодействия, развития региональных лабораторий контроля качества, подготовки квалифицированных специалистов и формирования культуры качества среди потребителей и производителей.

Ключевые слова: качество продукции, управление качеством, защита прав потребителей, метрология, стандартизация, техническое регулирование, правовые основы, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of New Uzbekistan, ensuring the population’s access to high-quality products has become an important strategic priority. In accordance with the newly adopted Constitution, the state is entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding citizens’ right to a healthy life, including access to safe and high-quality products. This constitutional provision establishes a solid legal foundation for strengthening product quality management mechanisms and enhancing consumer protection.

At the same time, since the early years of independence, the Government of Uzbekistan has paid considerable attention to the protection of consumer rights. The adoption of the Law “On Consumer Rights Protection” laid the foundation for regulating issues related to product quality, including product safety, certification, defects, warranty obligations, shelf life, and the return of products that do not meet established quality requirements. The law comprehensively defines the content of these legal relationships and provides a regulatory framework governing all aspects associated with the purchase and consumption of quality products.

According to the analysis, the general principles and characteristics of product quality management practices in the country are reflected in the new edition of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law “On Consumer Rights Protection.” At the same time, the specific legal framework governing these processes includes the Laws “On Metrology,” “On Standardization,” and “On Technical Regulation” (see Table 1).

The rationale for this classification can be explained by the following considerations.

First, general legislation. This group of legal acts consists of regulatory documents that establish a system of measures, obligations, rights, and guarantees aimed at ensuring the population's access to quality products. In particular, these documents regulate issues related to the circulation of products that do not meet established quality requirements in consumer markets, as well as matters arising during their purchase and use, with a primary focus on protecting consumer interests.

Second, special legislation. This group includes regulatory legal acts governing the organization of production processes, the establishment of technical and technological regulations, the standardization of measurement systems, and the determination of consumer and technical characteristics of products. It also covers legal provisions related to certification procedures and the assessment of product conformity with established standards and technical requirements (Table 1).

Table 1
Regulatory and Legal Framework for State Regulation of Product Quality Management in Uzbekistan¹

№	Regulatory Document	Content and Significance
I. General Legislation		
1.1	Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Establishes general norms and guarantees regarding citizens' rights and the state's obligations to ensure the provision of high-quality products to the population.
1.2	Law "On Consumer Rights Protection"	Regulates the provision of quality products to consumers, including liability for the sale of substandard goods, as well as the protection and enforcement of consumers' rights and legal interests.
II. Special Legislation		
2.1	Law "On Metrology"	A regulatory act aimed at ensuring the accuracy and uniformity of measurement units used in the production process of products.
2.2	Law "On Standardization"	Regulates the establishment of state standards for product quality and ensures their implementation and compliance.
2.3	Law "On Technical Regulation"	Defines the system for standardizing production processes, certification, and conformity assessment of products and services in accordance with established requirements

According to the conducted analysis, several areas for further development have been identified in the state regulation of product quality management in the country. These areas relate to the normative-legal, institutional, and practical dimensions of promoting and implementing quality management principles. Strengthening these aspects can contribute to the continuous improvement of product quality management mechanisms, enhance the effectiveness of consumer protection measures, and support the broader adoption of modern quality management practices.

The findings also indicate the importance of further improving regulatory frameworks, institutional coordination, and quality-oriented business practices. Addressing these areas will facilitate the more effective implementation of quality management principles and contribute to sustainable economic development and increased consumer confidence.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In our view, based on the current priorities in the field of state regulation of product quality management practices, it is appropriate to implement the following measures in the coming years.

Firstly, legislation should be further improved by strengthening the practical mechanisms of existing normative and legal documents related to quality control. In particular, it is necessary to develop a national system of standards that is harmonized with international quality standards.

Secondly, institutional reforms should be deepened by establishing coordination councils among authorized bodies involved in the state regulation of product quality management practices. In addition, regional quality control laboratories and centers should be established across different territories.

Thirdly, human resource capacity should be improved through the development of educational programs in higher education institutions aimed at training specialists in quality management and enhancing their professional qualifications.

Fourthly, technical and financial support mechanisms should be expanded. This includes developing a system of subsidies and grants for manufacturing enterprises that have implemented or are in the process of implementing international quality standards, as well as introducing digitalized product quality control systems in domestic markets.

Fifthly, a quality culture should be promoted among the population and business entities. This can be achieved by

¹ author's development

increasing public awareness of consumer rights and developing effective communication mechanisms to form a common understanding of product quality between consumers and producers.

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muhandislik

& iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025

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"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

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